

Investigating phytoremediation potential of *Brassica nigra* in removal of nickel, zinc and arsenic from contaminated soils

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Manuscript received online 21 June 2014, revised 28 July 2014, accepted 09 October 2014

Abstract : Phytoremediation is a technology for removing pollutants from the environment or making them inactive. The current study was carried out to examine phytoremediation capability of black mustard (*Brassica nigra*) for cleaning up the soil contaminated with nickel, zinc and arsenic. To this end, the germination capability of black mustard in remediation of the soil contaminated with different concentrations of nickel, zinc and arsenic ((control sample 0 ppm), 100 ppm, 500 ppm, 5000 ppm, 10000 ppm and 50000 ppm) was examined with three replicates for 120 days. As the obtained results suggest, in high concentrations of nickel, zinc and arsenic (up to 50000 ppm), germination was reduced 90% compared to the control sample. However, no significant difference was observed between the concentrations of 10000 ppm and 50000 ppm in this respect. The lowest germination percentage of 1 ± 0.57 was observed in soils with contamination concentration of 50000 ppm. Comparing the concentrations of nickel, zinc and arsenic in the case soil samples containing black mustard with that of the control samples, it was showed that concentrations of heavy metals have declined 944, 22, 426 and 0.276 ppm in the case samples. The uptake results in the case samples showed that the highest and lowest of the plant up-take were related to zinc (equal to 26.4 ppm) and arsenic (equal to 0 ppm), respectively. Although phytoremediation is a suitable method for reduction of nickel, zinc and arsenic, however studies showed that at concentrations higher than 500 ppm, the method is no longer efficient.

Keywords : Soil pollution, black mustard, phytoremediation, nickel, zinc and arsenic, germination, growth, heavy metals.

Introduction

Heavy metals are a group of metals with a density greater than 5 g cm^{-3} ¹. They are considered among the most important environmental contaminants. Their toxicity is regarded a growing, particular problem for ecology, food and environment². The heavy metal pollution is mainly originated from industrial activities such as mining, metal refining, metalworking fluids, exhaust fumes, fuel and energy production, fertilizer and pesticides and municipal waste recycling³. There are many chemical, physical and biological methods to remove heavy metals from the contaminated soils. Physical and chemical methods are expensive and usually recommended for severe contamination situations while biological methods are of inexpensive methods. In phytoremediation, proper selection of plant species has a special importance⁴⁻⁶. Researchers around the world have introduced a variety of plants for phytoremediation purposes depending on climatic conditions as well as contamination rates. In gen-

eral, it is necessary to select those plant species which are resistant to the pollutants with maximum germination, growth and root surface area.

There have been an enormous number of studies involving various aspects of phytoremediation, a few of which are mentioned here. Veerle *et al.* (2006) examined accumulation ability of cadmium in *Brassica napus* under laboratory conditions. They concluded that *Brassica napus* has suitable capability for phytoextraction of moderately heavy metal contaminated soils⁷. Greenberg *et al.* (2007) assessed the impact of a multi-process phytoremediation system for removal of pollutants from saline soils contaminated with oil products. They found that the multi-process system reduces a variety of organic contaminants in soils with accelerated remediation kinetics⁸. Page *et al.* (2006) conducted a research to investigate the redistribution of heavy metals in lupin plants (*Lupinus albus* cv. *Amiga*) through labeling the root for 24 h with radio-nuclides. They finally concluded that cluster roots con-

tained higher concentrations of all heavy metals than non-cluster roots⁹. Li *et al.* (2003) presented an article in order to economic and technical justification of developing a technology for commercial phytoextraction of nickel. In this research, with emphasis on ecotypes of *Alyssum* it was stated that phytoextraction of nickel can be developed by applying genetic technologies as well as two agents of desire agriculture and genetic-cumulative attributes of nickel¹⁰. Baker *et al.* (1994) presented an article entitled "Heavy metal accumulation and tolerance in British populations of the metallophyte *Thlaspi caerulescens* J. and *C. presl* (Brassicaceae)". In this research, uptake, accumulation and tolerance of heavy metals showed unexpectedly high tolerance to metals not present at elevated concentrations in the parent soils. Jain investigated capability of ryegrass for uptake of heavy metals in soils surrounding rim roads. In this paper, the reduction rate of six contaminant heavy metals including lead, chromium, manganese, copper, nickel and zinc were measured¹¹. In 2005, Ghosh and Singh carried out a research entitled "A review on phytoremediation of heavy metals and utilization of its byproducts". This research reviewed the status of phytoremediation technologies with an emphasis on phytoextraction of soils contaminated by heavy metals¹². Kumar Sharma *et al.* (2007) measured heavy metal contamination of soil and vegetables in suburban areas of Varanasi, India. They assessed the impacts of the wastewater irrigation on heavy metal contamination of *Beta vulgaris* (palak)¹³.

The current study was carried out to investigate capability of black mustard to remediate nickel, zinc and arsenic from contaminated soils.

Material and methods :

Preparation of soil samples :

Soil samples contaminated with heavy metals were taken from drilling logs of Broumi Village situated in Ahvaz-Mahshahr Road, 13 km away from Ahvaz City. The samples were mixed with non-contaminated soils and poured into pots. After outdoor air-drying, some amount of the soil was compacted. All containers and equipment were washed twice, once with 0.1 N HCl and then with double-distilled water. To ensure drying, they were placed in oven. The soil samples were also accurately weighed using a digital scale sensitive to 0.001 mg¹⁴. This re-

search was conducted in a completely randomized design with 6 treatments (control sample, 100 ppm, 500 ppm, 5000 ppm, 10000 ppm and 50000 ppm), one treatment plant (black mustard) and 3 replications. The LSD test was run in SPSS software to compare the up-take averages.

Determination of soil characteristics :

Some physical and chemical characteristics of the soil such as soil texture were determined by the methods; hydrometer analysis, electrical conductivity of the saturated soil-paste extract and soil reaction in saturated mud. Available phosphorus was measured by Olsen method¹⁵. Available sodium and potassium were determined using Ammonium Acetate Extraction Method and read by a flame photometer¹⁶. The Kjeldahl method was applied to measure the Total Nitrogen (TN) while lime was measured by titration with sodium hydroxide (caustic soda)¹⁷.

Measuring total concentration of heavy metals in the soil :

After passing the samples through a 63-micron sieve, 0.5 g of it was taken and added to 0.5 ml of aqua regia (3 : 1 HCl : HNO₃ ratio) and 3 ml of concentrated perchloric acid. Then, the samples were heated on a sand bath until almost being dried. After filtering the solution using Whatman filter paper No. 42, the filtered water was brought to a volume of 50 ml the samples were kept in sealed glass containers in the refrigerator (at 4 °C). Finally, the total concentration of the elements was read by atomic absorption device¹⁴.

Preparation of plant samples :

The black mustard plant samples were fully harvested (all plant organs) from the same place the soil samples were taken. Plants harvested from each pot have the same size and age. After transferring to the laboratory, the samples were washed with double-distilled water and drained. Then, all the samples were washed with 0.1 N HCl and double-distilled water once more. After outdoor drying, they were placed in the oven with 60°C for 24 h, powdered by an electric steel mill, and finally, stored in specific plastic containers.

Chemical digestion of plant samples :

1 g of the powder plant measured by a digital scale sensitive to 0.001 g was taken. Then, 5 ml of concen-

trated nitric acid was added to the samples. After spending 6 h, the samples were placed on hot plates with a temperature of 75 °C. Heating was begun gently until a brown vapor was raised. After 5–10 min, 10 ml of a solution containing a mixture of three acids (a ratio of 5 : concentrated nitric acid, 1 : concentrated sulfuric acid and 2 : concentrated perchloric acid) was added to each sample. Then, they were heated more severely until oxidation of the plant materials is completed. The heating was continued until the sample size was reduced to 3–2 ml and the samples were completely colorless. Adding 5–3 ml of the solution containing the three mentioned acids and re-heating, the blackened samples were returned to the normal condition. 1–2 ml of sulfuric acid was used to eliminate white deposits at the bottom of some samples. After being completely colorless and reducing the volume to 3–2 ml, the samples were brought to a volume of 50 ml by distilled water. Subsequently, they were placed in glass containers for reading by atomic absorption device. It should be mentioned that a control sample was prepared by passing all the mentioned above steps. It contained all the materials except for the plant samples¹⁸.

Results and discussion

Germination percentage of black mustard :

Germination percentage in the case samples containing mustard plants showed that the germination percentage in non-contaminated soils is 90% less than the soil with contamination concentration of 50000 ppm. It should be mentioned that higher percentage of germination (60%) was observed in soils with contamination concentration of 10000 ppm. Comparison of the case samples indicated that the lowest germination percentage of 10% was observed in soils with contamination concentration of 50000 ppm. The soil samples with contamination percentages of 10000 and 5000 ppm allocate themselves the next lowest germination percentages, respectively. The obtained results revealed that increased concentration of the contaminants in the soil was associated with lower germination percentage so that the highest germination percentage was recorded from the control sample and those sample containing 100 ppm of contaminants. There was no significant difference between germination percentages at concentrations of 50000 ppm and 10000 ppm. Increased concentration of the heavy metals up to 100 ppm resulted

in no significant reduction in germination percentage. As Fig. 1 demonstrates, no significant difference was observed in germination percentage of black mustard at concentration of 500 ppm and below. A significant decrease in germination rate was observed at concentration of 5000 ppm and higher. The estimated linear relationship between the contamination rate in the soil and black mustard germination is given in eq. (1).

$$y = 8.514 + 0.0 x \tag{1}$$

For the linear model, R^2 was obtained equal to 0.76 representing that the prediction capability of the model is relatively good.

Fig. 1. Germination percentage of black mustard as well as significant differences of the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

The uptake rates of nickel, zinc and arsenic by black mustard :

As Fig. 2 suggests, the nickel uptake at concentration of 100 ppm was increasingly higher than the other stations (equal to 8.31 ppm). There was observed no signifi-

Fig. 2. The nickel rate in black mustard as well as significant difference of the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

cant difference between two treatments of 500 ppm and 5000 ppm. Nickel uptake was significantly reduced (equal to 7.71 ppm) in the treatment with a concentration of 1000 ppm. The treatments with concentrations of 0 and 100 ppm have no significant difference in terms of arsenic up-take. At concentration of 500 ppm, arsenic up-take rate was suddenly increased to 0.35 ppm and then, declined once again to 0.20 ppm. In terms of nickel up-take, such a peak was observed in the treatment with concentration of 100 ppm.

The concentration of zinc element in black mustard revealed that the plant was absorbed appropriate amount of this element (20.29 ppm on average) in different treatments. The highest up-take rate of 26.43 ppm was reported from the 100-ppm treatment. However, in the treatment with concentration of 50000 ppm, a small amount of zinc (equal to 11.57 ppm) was absorbed by the plant buds.

As Fig. 5 suggests, black mustard has suitable capability in absorption of zinc. In overall, zinc up-take is higher than nickel concentration. The least absorption was related to the arsenic.

The average results obtained from different stations were analyzed using one way ANOVA and LSD test.

Concentration of heavy metals nickel, arsenic and zinc in the herbal treatments with different pollution levels showed a significant difference at level of 0.05 compared to the control sample ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. The arsenic rate in black mustard as well as significant difference of the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

Relatively good absorption of zinc, nickel and arsenic in case samples showed that in spite of harsh environmental conditions (water and oxygen deficiencies), this plant enjoys proper capability in absorption of the con-

Fig. 4. The zinc rate in black mustard as well as significant difference of the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

sidered heavy metals¹⁹. By acidifying the zone surrounding the roots, absorbent plants such as black mustard are able to uptake elements through entering them into the soluble phase²⁰. Secretion of various substances including enzymes from the black mustard root accelerates the decomposition of pollutants²⁰. Metal concentrations in plants are changed by their variation in soil. According to regression analysis, there is a significant, direct relationship between the amount of zinc, nickel and arsenic in the soil and in the black mustard²¹.

Relatively good absorption of zinc by black mustard indicates that this plant has an adequate capability for removal of zinc from contaminated soils. In concentration of 100 ppm, increased uptake of heavy metals was recorded due to physical and photochemical conditions as well as the presence of microorganisms in the soil. The concentration of 500 ppm is also suitable for phytoremediation²². A significant difference was observed in germination percentage of different treatments ($P < 0.05$). Generally, increased concentration of pollutants in soil reduces germination percentage of plant seeds²³. Average germination percentage of the plant at concentrations of 0 and 100 ppm was 100%. In other words, this concentration imposes a limited, negligible impact on germination percentage so that the seeds have still enough ability to absorb water and oxygen. However, in concentration of 50000 ppm, the seeds will not be able to supply their needs from the contaminated environment. No significant difference was observed in germination percentage of black mustard at the concentration of 500 ppm. The average germination percentage at concentration 500 ppm was equal to 93%. A significant decrease in germination rate was observed in the treatment of ≥ 5000 ppm. Delay in germination was reported at the concentrations of 10000 ppm and 50000 ppm. Average germi-

Fig. 5. Comparison of total concentrations of metals, nickel, arsenic and zinc in black mustard.

nation percentage in the treatments 5000 ppm, 10000 ppm and 50000 ppm were equal to 10%, 40% and 63%, respectively. It is worth noting that plant treatment buds at concentration of 50000 ppm were very weak and dark brown in irregular shape representing high toxicity by heavy metals. Around 5% of the buds decayed and dried out due to severe soil pollution. In other words, no plant grew at the concentration of 50000 ppm. Accordingly, the concentration was introduced as a critical concentration that reduces germination. Sprouts grew at other concentrations. The growth rate was different depending on the amount of pollution. The findings also showed that there is highly significant correlation between concentrations of the metals nickel (0.66%), arsenic (0.82%) and zinc (0.81%) in black mustard and different levels of pollution.

Given the proven role of the plant in refining soils contaminated with heavy metals and due to the fact that phytoremediation requires no special facilities, this method can easily apply in locations with low to moderate pollution. It can be considered as a suitable method for removing this kind of contaminants. In addition to cleaning up, green space created by the plants is also another advantage of this method²⁴. The plant response to high concentrations of heavy metals is in two forms. The first mechanism is avoidance by which plants prevent the uptake and transport of metals inside their cells. Those plants adopting this strategy are called non-cumulative. The second mechanism is the accumulation and compartmentalization of metals. Plants with this mechanism have a very

high capacity for metal uptake by roots as well as transport and store it in their shoots. These plants are called the excessive cumulative²⁰. They could be used for removal of heavy metal and cleaning up of contaminated soils through phytoremediation process. According to Baker and Reeves, "excessive-cumulative" term was first used by Jaffre *et al.* in 1976. Acidifying the zone surrounding the roots, absorbent plants such as black mustard are able to uptake elements through entering them into the soluble phase²⁰. Secretion of various substances including enzymes from the roots of lack mustard accelerates decomposition of pollutants²⁰. Their bioaugmentation is of factors that can help significantly to more and quicker cleanup of contaminated environments. Low uptake of arsenic in black mustard compared to soil is due to limited ability of plants for absorbing the metal. In other words, the plant is not able to absorb it surplus to its needs. Thereby, the average arsenic absorption by black mustard followed a downward trend. Zinc absorption in black mustard is more than nickel. In this sense, black mustard is a super absorbent plant.

Conclusion

Black mustard has a good capability for cleaning up soils contaminated with zinc. Therefore, black mustard can be a suitable adsorbent for this metal. No significant difference was observed between the amount of pollution in soil and black mustard germination. In general, increasing the concentration of contaminants in soil is led to a reduction in germination percentage of the seeds²³. Given the proven role of the plant in refining soils con-

taminated with heavy metals and due to the fact that phytoremediation requires no special facilities, this method can easily be applied in locations with low to moderate pollution. It can be considered as a suitable method for removing this kind of contaminants. In addition to cleaning up, green space created by the plants is also another advantage of this method. This is in consistence of the findings of Scanlon in 1991²⁴.

Acknowledgement

The authors have no conflict of interest to be declared. Special thanks for the services rendered by Ravian Danesh Mohit Company (Ravian D.M.) in providing insightful comments and proof-reading of the manuscript.

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